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METICOS

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D1.1

H – Requirement No. 2

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Editor(s):	Pantelis Velanas (EUC)
Contributor(s):	Giannis Spyropoulos (EUC) Christiana Themistocleous (EUC)
Reviewer(s):	Mohamed Abomhara (NTNU) Vagelis Papakonstantinou (VUB) Franck Dumortier (VUB)
Approved by:	All Partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	All Partners

Abstract:	This deliverable presents the initial versions of the templated for the informed consent forms and information sheets that will be used as the mean for recruiting human participants in METICOS project.
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Disclaimer	This deliverable reflects only the author’s views and views and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

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Terms and abbreviations

BCP	Border Control Points
EC	European Commission
EGE	European group on ethics

Executive Summary

This Deliverable D1.1 addresses the Ethics Requirement No. 2¹ - provided by the **Ethics Summary Report** as part of the **Horizon 2020 Ethics Appraisal Procedure**. Specifically, this deliverable concerns the requirement that is raised in the situation in which human participants are involved in the research (i.e. volunteers for social sciences, survey/questionnaire participants, interviewees etc.).

Deliverable D1.1 describes the procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants during METICOS project lifetime. Further to this, the informed consent/assent procedures (e.g., project information sheet) that will be implemented for the participation of humans including human participation and data protection issues are included.

This deliverable also examines the issue of incidental findings during research carried out under the METICOS project. It complies with the obligation to address the possibility of discovering incidental findings and describe in advance the procedure that shall be followed. To this end, this Deliverable identifies the issues related to incidental findings in research, developing the basic elements of a relevant policy, and then applies these findings onto the METICOS project circumstances. Even if it is unlikely to incur incidental findings during the METICOS project, this Deliverable defines a relevant procedure.

The document is structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides a short description of the METICOS project's data sources;
- Section 2 provides a description of research activities involving humans beings;
- Section 3 sets out the categories of research participants in the research activities;
- Section 4 sets out the informed consent/assent procedures;
- Section 5 recalls the definition of incidental findings in the research context and the basic elements of a relevant policy;
- Section 6 provides details about METICOS incidental findings policy;
- Section 7 provides the conclusions of this deliverable.
- The Annexes contain templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (both in language and terms intelligible to the participants) tailored to specific research activities.

¹ H - Requirement No. 2: "The procedures and criteria that will be used to identify/recruit research participants must be submitted. The informed consent/assent procedures that will be implemented for the participation of humans including data protection issues must be submitted. Templates of the informed consent/assent forms and information sheets covering the voluntary participation (humans) and data protection issues (both in language and terms intelligible to the participants) must be submitted. Details on incidental findings policy must be submitted."

1 Short description of the METICOS project's data sources

In order to fulfil its purposes, the METICOS project intends to exclusively collect data from two categories of data sources:

1. Primary Data: Primary data is the type of data that is collected directly from informed and consented participants during the METICOS project activities and during pilots at the Border Control Points. This is the type of data that is collected directly from human participants and which originates from questionnaires, surveys, interviews, workshops and pilots.
2. Secondary data: Secondary data is the type of data that is relevant to METICOS but has been collected in the past. Such data are already available to use in the context of the project from existing sources. There are two types of such secondary data:
 - a) Anonymous statistical data originating from border crossing points' databases such as Checked passengers per flight/day, Waiting Time - using SBC technologies (average per passenger/per hour), Waiting Time - manual control (average per passenger/per hour), Queue length - using SBC technologies (average per passenger/ per hour), Queue length - manual control (average per passenger/ per hour), Number of passengers controlled by Border Guard (per month/per hour), Number of passengers who used ABC technologies (per month/per hour), Passenger Demographics & Profiles, Recurring travelers per origin/destination, Historical passenger data, Number of access attempts with documents not accepted by the system - For BCP technologies, Number of access attempts with non-eligible documents - For BCP technologies, Number of access attempts with valid e-passport but biometric verification error - For BCP technologies, Number of complaints regarding SBC technologies (by date), Downtime of system per month/year - For BCP technologies, FAR / FRR - For BCP technologies, Total verification time - For BCP technologies, Total access time - For BCP technologies, Total time of biometric and document verification - For BCP technologies, Flight delays.

As regards secondary data collected from border crossing points' databases, the METICOS consortium decided to collect only data that has already undergone a prior anonymization process by the end-user organizations (border control authorities). Recital 26 of the GDPR defines "anonymous information" as being "information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person". As a reminder, the GDPR does not apply to the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes. However, the GDPR applies to the anonymization process itself.

In order to ensure that this anonymization process is carried out effectively by the end-user organizations before that the information is transmitted to the METICOS platform, it is planned to organize a workshop with MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS and CYPOL. This workshop will be dedicated to discussing the anonymization techniques being applied in order to avoid risks of re-identification. These anonymization techniques will be detailed in D3.6 – "Impact assessment and recommendations (final version)", due on M26.

- b) Data originating from social media: The aim is to retrieve any tweets publicly posted about Border Control Technologies and to mine the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies.

By consequence, it has to be noted that:

- no cameras will be used nor any type of sensors as data sources of the METICOS project. No such data from human participants will be collected.
- biometric data will not be collected as data sources of the METICOS project. No such data from human participants will be collected.
- data directly from travel documents will not be collected. It was considered that it is not necessary for the purposes of the METICOS project to collect information enabling the individualization of each traveler/border control staff member (first name, last name, date of birth, travel document number, etc.).
- personal data from Border Control Databases such as VIS, SIS, EES, ETIAS, etc will not be collected. It was considered that such extremely sensitive data were absolutely not needed for the purposes of the project.

2 Description of Research Activities involving Human Beings

Given that the purpose of the METICOS project is to measure the efficiency of border control technologies as well as to evaluate the users' acceptance of such technologies, data concerning two different sets of "users" are being collected:

- a) Data related to travelers;
- b) Data related to border control staff.

Hence, in several of its tasks, activities of METICOS will require the participation of these categories of humans. Such activities include the following types:

- 1) Workshops and interviews;
- 2) Questionnaires and surveys;
- 3) Sensing of social networks;
- 4) Pilots.

Each activity involving human beings is being described in the sections below, including information regarding the responsible task leader, relevant information from the DoA, a description of the purpose of the activity and whether the activity is being conducted in a publicly accessible area.

2.1 Workshops and interviews

Table 1 - Description of workshops and interviews

Task & Leader	Relevant information from DoA	Description and purpose of activity involving the participation of human beings	Is this activity performed in a publicly accessible area ² ?
T3.2 (VUB)	“Consult with relevant project stakeholders and external stakeholders (e.g., technical experts, lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, citizens, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, as well as others) to validate the analysis”.	Organization of workshops with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ethical Board (which is composed of internal and external experts) - Each partner’s DPO - Other identified external experts in the field of privacy The aim is to obtain feedback on the Data Protection Impact Assessment conducted in T3.2.	No (workshops will be organized in non-public sessions on Teams).
T3.3 (VUB)	“Host a virtual workshop with partners and external stakeholders to evaluate findings and to together weigh the impact by asking how METICOS will contribute to equality, dignity and autonomy, as well as to assess the foreseen impact on gender relations”.	Organization of a workshop with: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ethical Board (which is composed of internal and external experts) - external stakeholders such as lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, etc. The aim is to obtain feedback on the Human Rights Impact Assessment conducted in T3.3.	No (workshops will be organized in non-public sessions on Teams).
T3.4	“Finally, METICOS shall involve actively policy-makers and decision-makers to this task, ensure the provision of	Workshops /consultation meetings will be organized with relevant	Task 3.4 is closely supported, given its nature, by the activities of Task 11.1 and WP11 in general. METICOS will exploit all

² Note: crawling social media is considered being conducted in publicly accessible area.

(ViLABS)	appropriate evidence and will use effective evidence dissemination and incentives”.	<p>stakeholders, experts and policy officials.</p> <p>The aim will be to support the activities of the task with external consultation and guidelines from experts as well as to receive input in line with the expectations of the task on the different stages of implementation.</p>	<p>possible opportunities to communicate, disseminate as well as to actively engage all relevant stakeholders, in relation to this task, policy officials and decision makers, in order not only to disseminate the activities of the task but also to include them in an active beneficial discussion/feedback extraction “session”. Activities organised by METICOS as well as third party activities will be exploited the best way possible. For the activities to be organized by METICOS, those will be structured in the form of webinars and online workshops/roundtables of discussion, publicly available on the project communication channels and via the internet. All participants will be informed in advance about the purposes and goals of the activities as well as of the fact that those webinars will be recorded and be available under the project YouTube channel. The final conference will also be exploited as an opportunity to disseminate the results to policy officials and relevant stakeholders.</p>
T4.2 (CYPOL)	“Following detailed interviews with end-users, this task will lead to the creation of the necessary models for the high-level analysis of the technology acceptance processes of the cross- border domains introduced by METICOS”.	Analysing the actual actors and procedures involved in the business sectors of border control technologies. To achieve that, we will interview key police officers.	These interviews will take place at the Cyprus Policy HQ or/and via online platforms (depending on the applicable restriction in relation to COVID that will be in place at the time).
T6.4 (NTNU)	“This task will manage the testing and validation of the integrated platform before running the pilot scenarios”. According to the WP objectives: “organizing a workshop to mainly validate recommendations on the improvement of the EU perception abroad”.	The main purpose of the workshop is to validate the Social Sensing Toolkit’s results and improve/enhance the results by collecting comments and feedbacks from the workshop participants.	The workshop will be organized and planned for a limited participants in a form of physical meeting or a webinar. In case of the physical meeting (depends on the COVID restrictions) the venue of the workshop will be at the NTNU.
T10.2 (PPA)	“Further to this the objective of this task is to validate the content produced by the METICOS Platform during the Pilot #1, by conducting a workshop. The presence of end users at the workshop, with a particular effort to invite border management professionals, will enable to	Workshop with end-users (with a particular effort to invite border management professionals).	The workshop will be organized and planned for a limited participants in a form of physical meeting or a webinar. In case of the physical meeting (depends on the COVID restrictions) the venue of the workshop will be at the PPA premises.

	assess the added value of the platform with regard to their practical needs, constraints and experiences”.		
T10.3 (JOAFG)	“Further to this the objective of this task is to validate the content produced by the METICOS Platform during the Pilot #2, by conducting a workshop with EU stakeholders and border authorities”.	Workshop with EU stakeholders and border authorities.	The workshop will be organized and planned for a limited participants in a form of physical meeting or a webinar. In case of the physical meeting (depends on the COVID restrictions) the venue of the workshop will be at the JOAFG.
T10.4 (JOAFG)	“This task has a twofold objective and will be implemented in two phases. In the first phase the aim is to prepare and train the involved end users for the respective trial scenarios. This action involves the circulation of proper documentation regarding the system’s features as well as the exhibition of its operation and capabilities in an educational setup. The aim during the second phase of the task is to evaluate the METICOS platform taking into account all parties involved in its operation”.	End-user training for the respective trial scenarios.	The workshop will be organized and planned for a limited participants in a form of physical meeting or a webinar. In case of the physical meeting (depends on the COVID restrictions) the venue of the workshop will be at the JOAFG.
T11.2 (ViLABS)	“Targeted workshops organized by METICOS in order to facilitate the exploitation activities of the project, further establishing communication channels with key industrial & targeted stakeholders”.	<p>Organisation of/ participation in workshops with relevant internal, and external stakeholders (Cluster members, other third-party projects, key industrial and targeted stakeholders).</p> <p>The aim will be to facilitate METICOS exploitation journey. Additional information will be available on D11.3 on project month 36.</p>	Both in public and non-public sessions according to whether they will take place online and offline – given the limitations and opportunities of each as well as given the nature of the discussion or the affiliations of the participants. In all cases, participants will be fully informed about the results of the discussions and the use of information (recordings, minutes, communication activities relevant to the workshop organized).

2.2 Questionnaires and surveys

Table 2 - Description of surveys and questionnaires

Task & Leader	Relevant information from DoA	Description and purpose of activity involving the participation of human beings	Is this activity performed in a publicly accessible area ³ ?
T3.5 (EDPD)	<p>“This task will aggregate stakeholders’ knowledge and insights, along with the METICOS own innovative contribution in order to formulate targeted recommendations about the benefits and limits of BDA as applied in social media”.</p>	<p>The aim of the questionnaire related to this task is to collect the feedback of the border control authorities (police officers/experts in border controls) about the feasibility, acceptability and suitability of the METICOS approach.</p>	<p>No, this activity will not be performed in a publicly accessible area. The questionnaires will be circulated to predefined internal and external stakeholders of METICOS.</p>
T4.2 (CYPOL)	<p>“We will also do field studies and develop different questionnaires addressing specific questions about land BCPs, its control routines and technologies it uses. Interactive and participative methods of exploratory debate, analysis and study, involving all stakeholders will be used.</p> <p>These questionnaires will focus on the specific needs and requirements of each of the stakeholders involved at a particular BCP. A report will provide minimum technical requirements for interoperability purposes and specification of common technologies for performing border checks will be developed based on the findings of the different questionnaires”.</p>	<p>We identified vital police members who are experts in control routines and technologies. Subsequently, we have filled questionnaires that focus on the specific needs and requirements of each of the stakeholders involved at a particular BCP.</p>	<p>No activities are publicly organized. The questionnaire will be distributed online and filled by respondents either on their desktop or mobile devices through a secure VPN connection.</p>
T5.2 (JOAFG)	<p>“Stakeholder involvement in the form of user surveys and trials will be performed that generate the required social acceptance ground truth data (input variables</p>	<p>Citizen Survey with TAM questionnaire for evaluating border control technology acceptance of travelers:</p>	<p>Cognitive pre-tests: no, they will be done in person at AIT lab facilities.</p>

³ Note: crawling social media is considered being conducted in publicly accessible area.

	<p>representing targeted influence factors along with user responses and behaviours) for the different target groups (citizens, border control staff). In addition, the user studies aim at verifying the technology experience theories previously identified in terms of their applicability to social acceptance modelling for smart border control solutions as well as at identifying necessary model extensions e.g. to accommodate the impact of cross-cultural differences.</p> <p>To this end, three large online surveys will be performed, two of them targeting citizens from eight representative EU countries (to address cultural influence factors) and one survey targeting border control staff. The surveys will address people’s awareness, opinions, expectations and likely acceptance of smart border control technologies”.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive pre-tests – AIT: In the course of the TAM questionnaire development a series of cognitive pretests with potential respondents will be undertaken to identify limitations regarding the content and formal aspects (wording, grammar, etc.) of the instrument in order to avoid systematic biases and unintended answering behavior later in the pilot/main survey. • Pilot Survey in Austria (sample of 400, 2 technologies as stimuli) as pretest of validity of the questionnaire <p>Main Survey in 8 countries (sample of 8.000, 5 technologies as stimuli).</p>	<p>Pilot and Main Survey: All surveys will be realized online and filled by respondents either on desktop or mobile devices. Hence the surveys can be filled in publicly accessible areas. The questionnaire will be only accessible for panelist registered in the pool of the commissioned agencies partners in Austria and the other countries.</p>
T10.2 (PPA) (JOAFG)	<p>“MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS, and CYPOL will conduct two rounds of expert based evaluations at its premises from the investment/financial analysis end-user perspective. This involves personal evaluation sessions with questionnaires and interview, follow the think-aloud protocol and/or focus groups as suitable.</p>	<p>Personal evaluation sessions with questionnaires and interview.</p> <p>A wide survey that will include citizens from 8 countries, which was run in WP5, Del.5.2. The survey was run in 8 EU countries with 1000 participants per country.</p>	<p>No – the sessions will take place in non-public sessions (in person or virtual meeting).</p> <p>All surveys will be realized online and filled by respondents either on desktop or mobile devices. Hence the surveys can be filled in publicly accessible areas. The questionnaire will be only accessible for panelist registered in the pool of the commissioned agencies partners in Austria and the other countries.</p>
T10.2 (PPA)	<p>“These trials will be further extended including the outcomes from a wide survey that will include citizens from 8 countries”.</p>	<p>A wide survey that will include citizens from 8 countries.</p>	<p>Yes, most likely (Tallinn Airport).</p>

T10.3 (JOAFG)	“JOAFG will conduct two rounds of expert based evaluations at its premises from the content producing end-user perspective. This involves personal evaluation sessions with questionnaires and follow the think-aloud protocol and/or focus groups as suitable”.	Within Personal evaluation sessions with questionnaires, data is collected by predefined forms as quantitative measures. On a voluntary base, an audio recording can be done to support the transcription of responses on the think-aloud protocol. If recording is rejected, the basic transcript done by a monitoring person has to be sufficient.	No.
T10.3 (JOAFG)	“These trials will be further extended including the outcomes from a wide survey that will include citizens from 8 countries”.	An EU wide survey that will include citizens from 8 countries.	The survey was carried out in T5.2. Cognitive pre-tests: no, they will be done in person at AIT lab facilities. Pilot and Main Survey: All surveys will be realized online and filled by respondents either on desktop or mobile devices. Hence the surveys can be filled in publicly accessible areas. The questionnaire will be only accessible for panelist registered in the pool of the commissioned agencies partners in Austria and the other countries.

2.3 Sensing of social networks

Table 3 - Description of social networks sensing activities

Task & Leader	Relevant information from DoA	Description and purpose of activity involving the participation of human beings	Is this activity performed in a publicly accessible area ⁴ ?
T6.2 (NTNU)	“Based on the nature of the specified source and the method for gathering data in practice the result of the analysis will be given in report D6.3. In the case of the social sensing toolkit, innovative big-data analytics tools will be used and documented into the same deliverable. The extracted perceptions will help other tasks to identify and eliminate possible threats for the Security of the EU”.	Successful implementation of border control technologies highly depends on user acceptance. Therefore, the purpose of extracting user perceptions is important to understand how a user perceives the technology in use. Due to the fact that, in the past, the user perception of technologies is already investigated in other domains (healthcare, e-learning, etc). However, to the best of our knowledge, no study has investigated into the user perceptions for border control technologies and it would be the first time done in METICOS project.	First, the Social Sensing toolkit will be tested/simulated in private area (NTNU lab). Then, after the integration of the toolkit with METICOS middleware, the whole component will be tested at the pilot sites (public areas).
T7.1 (ICCS)	“Public data, such as website and social media entries, will be collected using dedicated crawlers developed by corresponding partners. The existing web crawlers will be adjusted or extended as appropriate”.	The aim of this task is to gather openly accessible public data in order to provide input to the Data Analytics Engine of WP7, with the aim of assessing the factors which influence acceptance using data-driven techniques.	Yes, considering that crawling social media is considered being conducted in publicly accessible area.

⁴ Note: crawling social media is considered being conducted in publicly accessible area.

2.4 Pilots

METICOS will be demonstrated and validated both at land border and airports. This will involve two use case scenarios in at least four pilot areas (Greece, Cyprus, Romania, Estonia). No activities will be undertaken outside the EU.

The METICOS Pilot Areas are provided below:

Estonia:

Pilot in Tallinn Old City harbour B terminal.

Equipment to be validated: document reader/scanner, DERMALOG fingerprint reader/scanner and document control equipment.

Cyprus:

Pilot in Larnaka Airport

Equipment to be validated: Interactive borderXpress kiosks, Integrated passport reader (MRZ)

Greece

Pilot in BCP of Kipoi or at the Eleftherios Venizelos Athens International Airport

Equipment to be validated: Mobile finger print scanner, Smart Borders (ABC), passport scanner

Romania

Pilot in BCP MORAVIȚA Timișoara

Equipment to be validated: TBD

The diagram below shows how is envisaged for the pilot to take place. Details of the steps of the pilot and participant recruitment is set out in the tables of this section and section 3.4.

Table 4 - Description of the pilots

Task & Leader	Relevant information from DoA	Description and purpose of activity involving the participation of human beings	Is this activity performed in a publicly accessible area ⁵ ?
T10.2	“This task plans and implements validation trials at user partner ITPFT, PPA, EDPD and CYPOL for the METICOS prototype platform as well as specific sub-tools for professional end users in an investment management organisation. The trial involves border authority staff and practitioners and research analysts in the corresponding industry”.	<p>Pilot with sub-tools for BCP authorities. It is necessary to work with human beings as they are the target group of the METICOS project. Their feedback is necessary to evaluate the METICOS system in a contextual perspective.</p> <p>Pilot activities: Pilot in Tallinn Old City harbour B terminal https://www.ts.ee/en/old-city-harbour/.</p> <p>In Tallinn Old City Harbour B-terminal, we will use 2 to 4 lines, because we will try to have 40 participants. In the existing border control booths, we have a computer, a REGULA document reader/scanner, DERMALOG fingerprint reader/scanner and document control equipment.</p> <p>Students from Estonian Academy of Security Sciences do not need a permission from the school if the participation is based on volunteering. Schools ethics committee must be included when biometric data is collected, which is not the case for the METICOS project. It should be coordinated also with AS Tallinna Sadam (company who manages the property where the pilot takes place). As we also use real time consenting travellers, it should be coordinated with AS Tallinn Airport.</p> <p>The prototype will be introduced and the participating officers will be trained in good time before the pilot takes place.</p>	Partly publicly accessible.
T10.3 (JOAFG)	“This task plans and implements validation trials at user partners MoCP/EDPD, PPA, ITPFT, ASBGS and CYPOL for the METICOS prototype platform as well as specific sub-tools for	<p>Pilot with sub-tools for travelers’ end users.</p> <p>It is necessary to work with human beings as they are the target group of the METICOS project. Their feedback is necessary to evaluate the METICOS system in a contextual perspective.</p>	Yes, as we will also use real-time consenting travelers during the pilots.

⁵ Note: crawling social media is considered being conducted in publicly accessible area.

	travellers' end users. The trial involves technology validation and Users acceptance in a no-gate border control environment".		
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3 Categories of participants in the research activities

For the purposes of the activities described in section 2, the METICOS consortium has identified that human participants will include the following types of persons.

3.1 Workshops and interviews

Table 5 - Categories of participants in workshops and interviews

Task & Leader	Criteria and criteria to identify/recruit research participants	Description on how to ensure representative human participation (Representative sampling)	Method to obtain and demonstrating consent (or other lawful basis)
T3.2 (VUB)	<p>Participants to the workshop will be selected on the basis of their expertise in the fields of ethics or law.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The composition of the Ethical Board is described in D1.8 – “GEN - Requirement No. 11”. EB members declare that they have no conflict of interest at the time of appointment and that they undertake to inform the Consortium if any conflict of interest should arise in the course of providing their opinion or carrying out their duties. - The DPOs of all partners are listed in D1.3. <p>Other external experts will be identified by proceeding to searches in online research directories in the fields of privacy, data protection and AI law.</p>	<p>The Board is currently being composed of 3 men and 2 women. Two new members with expertise in AI and GDPR will be added to the Board (1 woman and 1 man). The new composition of the will be set out in D1.10. Should other members join the Ethical Board in the future we will continue to pay attention to gender balance.</p>	<p>An information sheet and a consent form will be sent to participants by e-mail before participation to the workshops.</p> <p>Furthermore, when activating the recording of the workshops on Teams, consent will be asked to participants.</p>
T3.3 (VUB)	<p>Participants to the workshop will be selected on the basis of their expertise in the fields of ethics or law.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The composition of the Ethical Board is described in D1.8 – “GEN - Requirement No. 11”. EB members declare that they have no conflict of interest at the time of appointment 	<p>The participants in the workshop will be both the project partners as well as external stakeholders such as lawyers, civil servants, privacy advocates, human rights experts, LEAs, immigration experts, etc. In order to ensure the protection of the interests of vulnerable groups, civil society organizations active in</p>	<p>An information sheet and a consent form will be sent to participants by e-mail before participation to the workshop.</p>

	<p>and that they undertake to inform the Consortium if any conflict of interest should arise in the course of providing their opinion or carrying out their duties.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Other external experts will be identified by proceeding to searches in online research directories in the fields of human rights and AI. 	<p>the fields of migration and human rights will be involved in the workshop.</p>	<p>Furthermore, when activating the recording of the workshop on Teams, consent will be asked to participants.</p>
<p>T3.4 (VILABS)</p>	<p>Participants in the workshops will be selected on the basis of their expertise in the fields of ethics, law, evidence-based policymaking, border control, LEAs, EU funded projects and Policy Officials.</p>	<p>The participants in the workshop will be both the project partners as well as external stakeholders. Information to participate will be available to all. The panel members will be selected with attention to technical competence, gender, and geographical/cultural balance.</p>	<p>An information sheet and a consent form will be sent to participants by e-mail before participation in the workshop.</p> <p>All participants will be aware both of the recording as well as of the live streaming unless it is decided otherwise.</p>
<p>T4.2 (CYPOL)</p>	<p>Research participants are police officers. Due to European and National legislation and policies, Cyprus Police observed the rules for the Ethics.</p>	<p>All the research participants are key police officers who are experts in the field of National Border Control. The recruitment criteria for the participants are the following: Field of work (expertise)</p> <p>Gender (equally balanced - 50% Male or 50% Female)</p>	<p>Before having the interviews, all participants will participate in an internal workshop where they will be informed about the activities they will participate. These details will also be provided to them together with a consent form via email by the Cyprus Police, which the participant will have to sign if they agree to participate to such activities.</p>
<p>T6.4 (NTNU)</p>	<p>Participants to the workshop will be selected on the basis of their expertise in the fields of border control, technology, simulations, ethics, AI. Also, other stakeholders such as travellers (who will use the technology) will be invited to participate. The criterias to choose the participants will depend on participant's background, knowledge of the field, direct/indirect role in the METICOS or other projects, availability and interest.</p>	<p>The participants of the workshop will be chosen based on their background, expertise in the field, interest, etc that will ensure the representativeness of the samples.</p> <p>Note* factors such as age, gender and other demographics will not affect the invitation of the workshop participants and these factors will be taken in consideration.</p>	<p>An information sheet and a written consent form will be sent/given to the workshop participants before participating in the workshops. A written consent information will be given to the participants regarding the workshop (05-07 working days before the workshop).</p>

T10.2 (PPA)	All the participants will be adult volunteers.	Since we hope to include certain number of people for the interview, participants can register for the pilot until the number is reached. But because the interview is meant for border guard personnel, invitation will be sent to specific group only. The adult participants will be recruited based on volunteering. No specific age (above 18), gender, work experience is required, because they are volunteers.	A written informed consent will be provided.
T10.3 (JOAFG)	The advisory board and the end user organizations of METICOS will be the core of this workshop.	Feedback will be focused on the METICOS system. A representative study is not foreseen. It is focused on a discussion of results.	A written informed consent will be provided.
T10.4 (JOAFG)	End-User Partner will suggest the people to be trained. As mandatory factor, they have to voluntarily accept the informed consent and participation in the study.	Availability and free resources and personal acceptance to participate in the study are the guiding principles, not a matter of representability. Inclusion/Exclusion criteria are defined in T10.1	A written informed consent will be provided.
T11.2 (ViLABS)	The participants of the workshop will be the members of the consortium, synergies and cluster members, other EU funded projects as well as key industrial and other targeted stakeholders identified by the consortium and that could add value to the activities of task 11.2. Additional information will be available on D11.3 on project month 36.	Representative human participation will be ensured by adopting an intersectional approach.	Both in public and non-public sessions according to whether they will take place online and offline – given the limitations and opportunities of each as well as given the nature of the discussion or the affiliations of the participants. In all cases, participants will be fully informed about the results of the discussions and the use of information (recordings, minutes, communication activities relevant to the workshop organized).

3.2 Questionnaires and surveys

Table 6 - Categories of participants in surveys and questionnaires

Task & Leader	Criteria and criteria to identify/recruit research participants	Description on how to ensure representative human participation (Representative sampling)	Method to obtain and demonstrating consent (or other lawful basis)
T3.5 (EDPD)	Research participants are police officers/ external borders experts whose Organizations /Institutions have been defined from the partners of METICOS as internal/external stakeholders.	The questionnaire is addressed to the institutions/organizations which are defined by the partners of METICOS as internal/ external stakeholders. There are not addressed to specific persons. We will request from the organizations to respect gender equality and avoid discriminations.	A description of the METICOS platform is provided in appendix 2 of the questionnaire and the scope of providing their input is also described there. As a result by replying to the questionnaire they give their written consent that they are aware of the METICOS project and the scope of providing their input.
T4.2 (CYPOL)	Research participants are police officers. Due to European and National legislation and policies, Cyprus Police observe the rules for the Ethics.	All the research participants are key police officers who are experts in the field of National Border Control. The recruitment criteria for the participants are the following: Field of work (expertise) Gender (equally balanced - 50% Male or 50% Female).	The Cyprus Police will provide the details of the activity to all the participant during an internal workshop. All participants will have to provide a written consent if they agree to participate at this activity.
T5.2 (JOAFG)	<p>Pilot and Main Survey: The respondents are panelists registered in a pool for survey participation, able to fill an online survey on a digital device (i.e., computer, laptop, tablet, smartphone), getting an invitation for participating. Besides 200 participants per technology in each country relevant recruitment criteria is set in form of a screener including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gender (equally balanced 50% male and 50% female) • age categories (18-39 years, 40-64 years and 65-80 years) 	<p>For Pilot and Main Survey: The surveys will be carried out by an ISO 20252:2019-certified agency and the respective quality control only cooperating with equally certified suppliers. Representative sampling is ensured by the conceptualized screener/the set quotas as well as the sample plan of the agency, in regards of regional representation/incidence rate.</p>	<p>Cognitive Pre-Tests: An Informed consent form will be provided to participants to sign, content will be explained and open questions answered.</p> <p>Pilot and Main Survey: The Panelist register and confirm an informed consent (GDPR-conform) to participate in surveys at the panel provider, which carries out the questionnaire in cooperation with the agency contracted by JOAFG. Furthermore, at the start of the questionnaire not only purpose and project information, but also a contact email address is displayed for questions and complaints.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> travel frequency (between 2015 and 2019 at least one border crossing of EU external borders to non-EU borders and/or within the EU). 		
T10.2 (PPA) (JOAFG)	<p>All the participants will be volunteers. At this point, no specific criteria have been agreed on.</p> <p>The respondents are panelists registered in a pool for survey participation, able to fill an online survey on a digital device (i.e., computer, laptop, tablet, smartphone), getting an invitation for participating. Besides 200 participants per technology in each country relevant recruitment criteria is set in form of a screener including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> gender (equally balanced 50% male and 50% female) age categories (18-39 years, 40-64 years and 65-80 years) <p>travel frequency (between 2015 and 2019 at least one border crossing of EU external borders to non-EU borders and/or within the EU).</p>	<p>The surveys will be carried out by an ISO 20252:2019-certified agency and the respective quality control only cooperating with equally certified suppliers. Representative sampling is ensured by the conceptualized screener/the set quotas as well as the sample plan of the agency, in regards of regional representation/incidence rate.</p>	<p>Consent form provided with relevant information will be sent to the participants' prior personal evaluation sessions.</p> <p>If recording takes place, it will be informed also right before the session starts. Information about recording must include also how long and where recordings are stored, who has the access to the recordings and what is the purpose of recording.</p> <p>The Panelist register and confirm an informed consent (GDPR-conform) to participate in surveys at the panel provider, which carries out the questionnaire in cooperation with the agency contracted by JOAFG. Furthermore, at the start of the questionnaire not only purpose and project information, but also a contact email address is displayed for questions and complaints.</p>
T10.2 (PPA)	<p>All the participants will be volunteers.</p>	<p>Participants will consist of:</p> <p>a) Personnel of end users that are already working at the BCP that pilots will be held that volunteer to participate in the research as BCP officers.</p> <p>(b) Employees and other persons from the organisations of the partners (such as current and former students) that volunteer to participate in the research as travellers.</p>	<p>A written informed consent shall be provided via email or in hard copy and be collected prior to the commencement of the activity from all the participants.</p>

		(c) Real travellers that volunteer to participate in the research. Volunteers are going to be recruited by either posters at the border points or at JOAFGs volunteer pool, if applicable. The involvement of real travellers has not yet been confirmed by PPA.	
T10.3 (JOAFG)	Experts are nominated by the METICOS partners and must be related to the partner organization.	As it is an expert sample from METICOS, it is for the project representative.	A written informed consent will be provided.
T10.3 (JOAFG)	See 5.2 – the survey is done there. All data will be used from this survey.	See 5.2 – the survey is done there. All data will be used from this survey.	See 5.2 – the survey is done there. All data will be used from this survey.

3.3 Sensing of social networks

Table 7 - Categories of participants in social networks sensing activities

Task & Leader	Criteria and criteria to identify/recruit research participants	Description on how to ensure representative human participation (Representative sampling)	Method to obtain and demonstrating consent (or other lawful basis)
T6.2 (NTNU)	<p>We will be using Twitter social media platform for collecting research data specifically to this task. The criteria to identify/recruit research participants are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> We have created a list of keywords such as “e-gates”, “smart border control technologies”, “border control technologies”, “METICOS”, etc. (complete list is given in D6.2) to ensure that we only collect relevant tweets. Because, the tweets are relevant it means the users who posted the 	<p>Will depend on the pilot’s activity/samples representativeness.</p> <p>Our sampling approach is a “random sampling” relies of the “keyword-based” analysis. For instance, we collect tweets regarding border technologies using a keywords “#border_control, #border technology” between two time period (e.g., 2019 and 2022) by searching tweets at these different time points each day/month/year. Then we create a study sample by taking a random sample of number of tweets based on</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> With respect to the data collected from social media no consent is required due to the fact that the data is public and is anonymized (no identification of any individual). . The basis of lawfulness for the further compatible use of twitter data and online reviews is the legitimate interest of the METICOS joint controllers. Indeed, the “compatibility presumption” provided by Article 5 (1) (b) of the GDPR states that “further processing for [...] scientific research purposes [...] shall, in accordance with Article 89 (1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes”. According to the Article 29 Working

	<p>tweets will be automatically the relevant research participants.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Also, we will provide statistics related to the participants based on different demographics and profile information like age, gender, country, verified user or not, location, no. of followers, etc. 	<p>e.g., locations, countries etc. The random sampling allows for each member of the target group on Twitter to have an equal chance of being chosen and ensure unbiased representation of the larger Twitter population.</p>	<p>Party, “the fact that personal data is publicly available may be considered as a factor in the assessment, especially if the publication was carried out with a reasonable expectation of further use of the data for certain purposes (e.g. for purposes of research)” .</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • With respect to the data which will be collected from the pilot sites, an information sheet and consent form will be sent to participants in accordance to METICOS’s ethical guidelines.
<p>T7.1 (ICCS)</p>	<p>The criteria to select Twitter as the primary social media to crawl information are the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real-time access to information through API - Abundance of data - Possibility to access all historical twitter data through academic account <p>After selecting Twitter as a primary source of public data, we have defined the keywords in order to extract the information needed. Therefore, the results are limited to the terms “smart borders”, “automatic border control”.</p>	<p>As mentioned in the literature, any collection of tweets will be biased, and inferences based on analysis of such tweets will not match the population characteristics. On the other hand, what we aim to do to ensure representativeness, is firstly to include a multitude of languages (including underrepresented languages), secondly to explicitly mention the fact that bias is innate when processing Twitter data and lastly to ensure that many streams of data are included in the Machine Learning algorithms.</p>	<p>The tweets to be collected will contain personal data information. However, after retrieving the data, the tweet ID will be deleted, as per the anonymization guidelines discussed, since it is not needed for processing. As for the text of the tweet, this is public data as the users of Twitter have given consent to being published. Having said that-exact texts of the tweets collected will not be shared. Only aggregated results and conclusions driven from this data will be shared. Finally, the collected data will be deleted as soon as the models are trained sufficiently and only the aggregated results will be stored.</p>

For the type of activity consisting in crawling public social media data for the purpose of measuring social acceptance of border control technologies, it should be noted that consent is not the appropriate basis of lawfulness.

The aim of processing tweets in the context of METICOS project is to retrieve any tweets publicly posted about Smart Border Control Technologies and to mine the opinion, sentiment and acceptance of Twitter users related to these technologies. Through social media, users share self-expressions, opinions or general

thoughts and publicly self-reported activities; these are posted more spontaneously through social media, no guidance needed, and the information provided could be used from context-aware systems. To retrieve this information, a Twitter data collector application downloads any related tweets periodically and provides them as input to the Advanced Data Analytics Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data module. Twitter is used as the source of information, due to the public character of users' comments and the variety of information provided.

When creating an account on Twitter, the data subjects agree with the terms and conditions of the Twitter's privacy policy⁶ according to which "By publicly posting content when you Tweet, you are directing us to disclose that information as broadly as possible, including through our APIs, and directing those accessing the information through our APIs to do the same. To facilitate the fast global dissemination of Tweets to people around the world, we use technology like application programming interfaces (APIs) and embeds to make that information available to websites, apps, and others for their use - for example, displaying Tweets on a news website or analyzing what people say on Twitter. We generally make this content available in limited quantities for free and charge licensing fees for large-scale access. We have standard terms that govern how this data can be used, and a compliance program to enforce these terms".⁷

According to the Twitter standard terms that govern how public tweets can be used, "Unless explicitly approved otherwise by Twitter in writing, you may not use, or knowingly display, distribute, or otherwise make Twitter Content, or information derived from Twitter Content, available to any entity for the purpose of: (a) conducting or providing surveillance or gathering intelligence, including but not limited to investigating or tracking Twitter users or Twitter Content; (b) conducting or providing analysis or research for any unlawful or discriminatory purpose, or in a manner that would be inconsistent with Twitter users' reasonable expectations of privacy; (c) monitoring sensitive events (including but not limited to protests, rallies, or community organizing meetings); or (d) targeting, segmenting, or profiling individuals based on sensitive personal information, including their health (e.g., pregnancy), negative financial status or condition, political affiliation or beliefs, racial or ethnic origin, religious or philosophical affiliation or beliefs, sex life or sexual orientation, trade union membership, Twitter Content relating to any alleged or actual commission of a crime, or any other sensitive categories of personal information prohibited by law"⁸.

The basis of lawfulness for the collection of publicly available tweets is the consent of the data subject. The basis of lawfulness for the further compatible use of tweets for scientific research is the legitimate interest of the METICOS joint controllers. Indeed, the "compatibility presumption" provided by Article 5 (1) (b) of the GDPR states that "further processing for [...] scientific research purposes [...] shall, in accordance with Article 89 (1), not be considered to be incompatible with the initial purposes". According to the Article 29 Working Party, "the fact that personal data is publicly available may be considered as a factor in the

⁶ The Twitter privacy policy is available at https://cdn.cms-twdigitalassets.com/content/dam/legal-twitter/site-assets/privacy-june-18th-2020/Twitter_Privacy_Policy_EN.pdf

⁷ Ibid, p.5.

⁸ See the Twitter Developer Agreement at <https://developer.twitter.com/en/developer-terms/agreement>

assessment, especially if the publication was carried out with a reasonable expectation of further use of the data for certain purposes (e.g. for purposes of research)⁹”.

3.4 Pilots

Table 8 - Categories of participants in pilots

Task & Leader	Criteria and criteria to identify/recruit research participants	Description on how to ensure representative human participation (Representative sampling)	Method to obtain and demonstrating consent (or other lawful basis)
T10.2	<p>The trials of METICOS will involve existing personnel of YDEAP, PPA, ITPFT and CYPOL that are already working at the specific border control points (BCP). For each trial, a specific part of the border control and travellers monitoring section will be selected at the Tasks T4.1, T4.2 and T4.4 of the project. The selected areas at the BCP will be defined according to the requirements and specifications derived from task T4.2. A detailed observational plan (as part of the ethics guidelines to be delivered in D2.4 “Data Management Plan”) will be prepared in strict collaboration with the ethical component of the METICOS consortium.</p>	<p>In relation to employees of BCPs, there will be participants with various roles as described in the use cases of the project (Deliverable D4.2 – Task 4.4). More specifically, for the YDEAP End-user Pilot the research participants are those that hold the following positions: i) Border Police Officer; ii) Border Guard; iii) Custom Officer and Immigrant Officer. For the PPA End-user Pilot personnel with the following roles will be involved: i) Border Police Officer; ii) Border Guard; iii) Custom Officer and Immigrant Officer, ITPFT End-user Pilot personnel with the following roles will be involved: i) Border Police Officer; ii) Border Guard; iii) Custom Officer and Immigrant Officer, and for the CYPOL End-user Pilot personnel with the following roles will be involved: i) Border Police Officer; ii) Border Guard; iii) Custom Officer and Immigrant Officer.</p>	<p>A written informed consent shall be provided via email or in hard copy and be collected prior to the commencement of the activity from all the participants.</p>

⁹ Article 29 Working Party, Opinion 06/2014 on the notion of legitimate interests of the data controller under Article 7 of Directive 95/46/EC, adopted on 9 April 2014, WP217, p.39.

<p>T10.3 (JOAFG)</p>	<p>The following types of participants will be involved in the pilots:</p> <p>(a) Personnel of end users that are already working at the BCP that pilots will be held that volunteer to participate in the research as BCP officers.</p> <p>(b) Employees and other persons from the organisations of the partners (such as current and former students) that volunteer to participate in the research as travellers.</p> <p>(c) Real travellers that volunteer to participate in the research. Volunteers are going to be recruited by either posters at the border points or at JOAFGs volunteer pool.</p> <p>It is noted that for all the above categories of research participants only adult volunteers (with a capability to consent) will be recruited in each BCP pilot site. Vulnerable data subjects such as people with disabilities and minors will not participate in the research activities of METICOS. The recruitment method and informed consent procedures will be particularly stringent to ensure no coercion (not even soft or indirect) is exerted. The specific criteria for the selection of the volunteer participants are determined by the pilot requirements.</p>	<p>The pilot is focused on the test and implementation and function of the METICOS system. It is not aimed for to provide a representative sample but a proof of concept.</p> <p>The aim is to have approximately 80 participants per site/pilot and to gather quantitative and qualitative results with a ratio of approx. 50 volunteers to participate as travelers and 30 BCP staff. The partners will aims to ensure a gender and age balance in the selection of research participants. If such balance cannot be achieved, this will be recorded in the findings to avoid and address any discrimination or biases in the results.</p> <p>For the purposes of the use case/pilots, employees and other persons from the organisations of the partners (such as current and former students) that volunteer to participate in the research as travellers such.</p> <p>These research participants will mainly consist of employees of the partners participating in the pilots and current and former volunteer students of EUC, NTNU, ICCS, AIT and JOAFG. Other participants will consist of volunteers from the Police Academy (students) of EDPD and employees of PPA and other end-users.</p> <p>For the selection of volunteers, partners will do their best to ensure the best possible age, gender and ethnicity balance of the volunteers.</p> <p>In addition to the above, it will be possible to engage real travellers that volunteer to participate in the</p>	<p>All participants will sign an informed consent that declares their volunteering participation and acceptance of use of data for the purpose of METICOS. Recruitment procedures: 1. Information about the project and pilot purpose 2. Expected outcome for own organization 3. Expected actions to be done 4. Resources available 5. Time plan 6. Contact points for own action, contact point for project information and contact point for pilot. 7. Signature</p> <p>Just if a person has signed this informed consent, this person can participate in the pilot.</p>
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		<p>research. The aim is to set posters in the selected sites which will provide the required information on METICOS through a QR code. The traveller may scan the QR code with his/her mobile phone to participate in the research by answering certain questionnaires. The relevant privacy statements and consent forms will require the traveller's acceptance prior to he/she proceeds with the research activities.</p> <p>Also, real travellers will have the opportunity to provide their feedback on the acceptability of the BCP technologies by providing their input through a tablet that will be available at the selected sites. The tablet application will provide the traveller the opportunity if he/she wishes to choose his/her satisfaction level of the BCP experience (by selecting the relevant smiley face). More details of these technologies that will be used for METICOS are described in WP7.</p> <p>It is noted that current BCP technology in airports in Europe supports EU identification documents from countries of Schengen. Therefore, it may not be possible for volunteers that do not own identification documents from a country in Schengen to participate during the pilots as travellers.</p> <p>During pilots that will take place in land borders, it will be possible for real travellers to volunteer to participate in the research and it is anticipated that such volunteers will consist of EU and non EU nationals. Partners of METICOS that will aims to provide a sample of volunteers (ie employees/students) that are EU and</p>	
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		non EU nationals for the purposes of the land border pilots).	
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4 The informed consent/assent procedures

Specific measures to ensure the voluntary participation of participants and to protect these from a breach of privacy/confidentiality and potential discrimination will be applied, as it follows:

- **Confidentiality:** The names and date of birth of the participants in the trials will appear in the consent form to be signed in order to ensure accountability towards the European Commission with the aim provide evidence on request. It is noted that in relation to the participation of the real travellers, the name and date of birth of the real travelers will not be requested. The participation of volunteers (and their consent forms) will not be communicated to any third party. Moreover, the questionnaires and METICOS applications will not ask for any direct identifier (name, date of birth, etc), minimizing the risk of linkability with the data provided in the consent forms. All personal data stored during the trials will be erased four months after the completion of the METICOS Project.
- **Voluntary participation:** In order to ensure voluntary participation of employees of BCPs and of organizations of the METICOS consortium, the consent form must be signed minimum two days before participating to the pilots. To some extent, this will ensure that employees are not pushed to participate on the last minute. Moreover, it shall be ensured that their participation (or refusal) will have no adverse consequences.
- **Right to get more information:** In addition to all information which will be provided by METICOS (in the information sheet), the participants can ask any questions about the activities in which they participate at any time. The responsible Task leader will be available to answer their questions, interests or concerns about the activity involving human beings. In the event that further guidance is necessary, the Task Leader may revert to the project's ethics and legal scrutiny mechanisms.
- **Right to withdraw from participation:** During the activities involving human beings, if any volunteer wishes to not to continue the activity, he/she will have the right to do so, without having to give explanations and without being affected in any way. However, if during an activity, a participant has already provided information via questionnaires or via METICOS applications without providing any direct identifier, the rights of access cannot be exercised except if the participant provides additional information enabling his or her identification.
- **Informed Consent:** A detailed informed consent will be created for each activity involving human beings, fully outlining the scope of the activity and its purposes along with the data collected and analyzed.

METICOS will follow the opinion of METICOS Ethics Board that has been set up and of various external expert committees in the field (*e.g.* the European group on ethics (EGE) in science and new technologies to the European Commission and the European Data Protection Board). The METICOS Ethics Board review and comments will be set out in D1.9 and D1.10. Further, the relevant ethics committee of each partner of METICOS has provided an opinion/approval for the research with humans which are provided in D1.2.

In addition, all national legal and ethical requirements of the Member States where the research is performed will be fulfilled.

Finally, in the METICOS project, two specific tasks are specifically dedicated to ensure compliance with data protection norms and human rights:

- Task T3.2 aims to complete a comprehensive Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) of the METICOS platform. A DPIA is a process designed to describe the processing, assess its necessity and proportionality and help manage the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons resulting from the processing of personal data by assessing them and determining the measures to address them. In other words, a DPIA is a process for building and demonstrating compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other privacy requirements.
- Task 3.3 seeks to incorporate human rights as a fundamental axis of the METICOS platform and research activities, in order to prevent METICOS components from breaching fundamental rights.

Any data collection and storage involving humans will be strictly held confidential at any time of the research. Furthermore:

- all the data subjects (participants) will be informed and given the opportunity to provide their consent to any monitoring and data acquisition process;
- all the data subjects will be strictly volunteers (except for data collected from twitter – see section 3.3) and all test volunteers will receive detailed written (information sheet) and oral information;
- no sensitive data will be centrally stored. In addition, when feasible, as detailed in D1.4, data will be encrypted (data in transit or data in rest) and anonymized (when applicable) as well as abstracted (relevant and limited to the purposes for which they were collected) in a way that will not affect the final project outcome;

In addition, participants will receive in their own language the METICOS' information sheet which includes:

- a commonly understandable written description of the project and its goals including (not limited to) the purpose of data collection, type of data which will be processed, consequences of their participation and confidentiality of their data;
- the planned project progress and the related testing and evaluation procedures;
- privacy and data protection procedures;
- participants rights such as the possibility to decline the offer and to withdraw at any point of the pilot (and without consequences). However, if during a pilot a participant has already provided information via questionnaires or via METICOS applications without providing any direct identifier, the right of access, rectification and erasure cannot be exercised, except if the participant provides additional information enabling his or her identification;
- incidental findings policy;
- benefits, disadvantages and risks; and
- details of contact persons (contact of project coordinator, project data protection partner as well as the contact details of the Data Protection Officer of the activity's responsible partner).

The METICOS Ethical Board established by D1.8 will ensure that the METICOS informed consent is a process, not just a form as shown in figure 1 below. The summary of the procedure as follows:

- The METICOS project must be presented to the person to enable him/her to voluntarily decide whether to participate in METICOS project or not.
- METICOS representative should ensure that the person has the capacity (adult and capable of making decision) to understand the information provided in the METICOS information sheet and voluntary opt-in to the METICOS project.

Moreover, the Ethical Board established in D1.8 will scrutinize the research, to guarantee that there is no undue risk for the user. Thus, the Consortium shall implement the research project in full respect of the legal and ethical national requirements.

It is noted that the consent form and information sheet provided to the research participants will be tailored made for the specific activity the individual will participate at. Templates of METICOS' information sheet and informed consent/asset forms per activity are shown in Appendix I.

Figure 1: METICOS procedure for taking informed consent

5 Incidental findings in research

5.1 EU funding and incidental findings policy

Incidental findings policy as an ethic issue is addressed in the Commission’s guidance entitled “how to complete your ethics self-assessment”.¹⁰ The Commission has published these guidelines in order to help all Horizon 2020 programme applicants to get their proposal ethics-ready” for EU funding. Incidental findings policy is included in the ethics issues checklist published by the European Commission and in particular in its section 2 (humans). It is therefore concluded that this ethical obligation applies to research that involves human participants. If this is the case, namely a human subject research, the procedures that will be implemented in the event of unexpected incidental findings should be clearly stated (namely whether the participants have the right to know or not to know about such findings). In other words, researchers have an obligation to address the possibility of discovering incidental findings and describing in advance the procedure that shall be followed in such case acting both proactively (for instance acquiring consent forms by the participants), as well as following such findings (confidentiality, communication to research participants etc.).

If one considers the ethical implications such findings may raise for researchers and at the same time what implications their disclosure to participants may present, it becomes apparent that incidental findings present a range of ethical, legal, and practical challenges, for both their recipients, as well as the researchers who encounter them. Therefore, their inclusion in the ethic self-assessment checklist is considered essential. In order however to better understand these implications and their possible consequences in the context of research conduct, a definition should be included in this report.

5.2 Definition of incidental findings

The notion of incidental findings originated in medical and genetic research. In this context all existing definitions of incidental findings have a medical focus/orientation. For instance, a definition defines incidental findings:

“as test results that are outside the original purpose for which the test or procedure was conducted or incidental findings are observations of potential clinical significance unexpectedly discovered in research participants and unrelated to the purpose or variables of the study or the medical problems discovered in the course of a research/clinical trial which were not related to the topic of research or a finding concerning an individual research participant that has potential health or reproductive importance and is discovered in the course of conducting research but is beyond the aims of the study”

A practical example, in order to better understand what incidental findings are, involves for instance a medical study where the researcher comes across an unexpected abnormal finding, such as a brain tumor on a research neuroimaging scan of a volunteer.

¹⁰ http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/grants_manual/hi/ethics/h2020_hi_ethics-self-assess_en.pdf

The Presidential Commission for the Study of Bioethical Issues (Bioethics Commission) has issued a report for researchers under the title incidental and secondary findings. According to this report incidental findings can be either “anticipatable” or “unanticipatable.”

An **anticipatable** incidental finding is one that is known to be associated with a test or procedure. Anticipatable incidental findings need not be common or even likely to occur—their defining characteristic is that the possibility of finding them is known.

Unanticipatable incidental findings include findings that could not have been anticipated given the current state of scientific knowledge. Researchers cannot plan for these types of findings specifically. However, they can consider in advance what they might do if a particular kind of unexpected finding arises, for example, one that could be actionable or lifesaving.

5.3 Ethical concerns raised by incidental findings

The main ethical concern when incidental findings in research occur is whether or not these findings should be disclosed to research participants. Some of the questions the researchers ought to have answered in advance before commencing their research are:

- *How should a finding of potential clinical significance be handled in the research setting?*
- *Should it be communicated to the research subject or not?*
- *Who shall be responsible to evaluate potential risks and benefits of such disclosure and ultimately take the final decision of whether to communicate such findings or not?*
- *Should participant welfare be protected and privacy be safeguarded?*
- *What duties belong to basic research scientists who do not have medical training?*
- *Whose responsibility is it to communicate the finding to a subject, to follow up, and to treat if needed*

The answers to these questions bring to the surface further ethical concerns when incidental findings in research may raise. In more detail, possible implications these findings may have on participants should be taken into serious consideration: for example, will research subjects be ready to face the shock and anxiety that may be triggered by unwelcome and potentially bad news, can they afford the costs associated with follow-up, but most importantly do they want such findings to be communicated to them in the first place?

As far as researchers are concerned the main ethical concern that needs to be addressed is: are researchers ethically obligated to share such information with study participants and, if yes, are they qualified to do so? This obligation derives from the broader researcher duty of beneficence to secure participants’ well-being by maximizing benefits and minimizing harms. In other words, researchers have an ethical duty to plan for incidental findings to the best possible extent.

5.4 The role of incidental findings risk assessment

Given the constantly increasing number of people working in research today, the advanced medical technologies used and the number of people participating in research, the possibility of incidental findings is becoming increasingly common.

The best way to minimize the risks of incidental findings in research which may potentially entail for both researchers and participants, is the performance of a sound risk assessment.

The first step that needs to be undertaken when conducting a risk assessment is identifying incidental findings. The researchers should evaluate in advance the possibility of discovering incidental findings in their research, as well as the extent of such possibility. Once they identify the possibility of discovering incidental findings, they should recognize and list such findings first by stating if they are anticipated or anticipatable. The possibility of findings that could not be predicted at all, if existing, should also be taken into consideration. Management of incidental findings should be an important part of the risk assessment. Researchers at this stage should be able to categorize the findings and evaluate their magnitude and the significance and potential implications they may have to research participants, seeking expert consultation, if needed. This will affect the next step of the risk assessment, that is communication policy. Specifically, what are the incidental findings should be communicated. How shall these findings be communicated? Who is the person responsible to communicate them to research subjects? The final step of the risk assessment is designing a clear policy outlining what follow-up assistance will be provided. To this effect, the implementation of an appropriate plan for the incorporation of outside expertise to evaluate incidental findings and/or apply the best return and communication policy of such findings to their recipients, could prove very useful.

The main steps of the risk assessment could be summarized to the following:

1. Identify incidental findings;
2. Recognize and list incidental findings;
3. Manage incidental findings by categorizing and evaluating them;
4. Communicate them to research participants;
5. Design a follow-up policy.

Incidental findings therefore need to be taken into consideration when researchers design their consent forms. More specifically, researchers should inform potential research participants in the informed consent process and forms that:

- a. incidental findings may be found;
- b. describe to them the anticipated incidental findings that may arise;
- c. inform them of the process by which incidental findings will be evaluated;
- d. inform them of the circumstances under which they will be communicated to them, as well as of the disclosing process;
- e. indicate how participants might opt out of receiving certain findings;
- f. Most importantly, researchers should acquire the participants written and clear consent that they wish such findings, if any, to be notified to them.

6 The METICOS project: Could incidental findings occur during the METICOS research?

6.1 Project's Description

METICOS aims to introduce Big Data Analysis of border control information systems, in order to provide a step-change towards more modern and efficient Smart Border management and towards gaining societal and political acceptance of modern control technologies of EU borders such as “no gate solutions”. It is therefore positioned as an initiative to create a real-time decision-support system with regard to different Smart Border control technologies that empowers three major stakeholder groups within the European border control sector (i.e., travellers and border control authorities & service providers) to ensure user acceptance, secure positive societal impact and maximize border control process efficiency. To this end, the METICOS project will develop a platform that integrates information systems and networks of data sources in order to validate the efficiency and users' acceptance of border control technologies. The proposed platform will provide metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions. To maximize impact of the project, METICOS will join the European Initiative for Smart Borders and contribute aforementioned cross-border and cross-cultural Big Data Analysis and decision support systems that feature harvesting of multi-lingual and cross-sectorial data from heterogeneous sources, different analytics approaches and risk assessment methods.

METICOS will be demonstrated and validated both at land border and airports. This will involve two use case scenarios in at least four pilot areas (Greece, Cyprus, Romania, Estonia).

The Pilots will involve volunteers pretending to be travellers and officers acting in their capacity as cross border officers. The aim is to have approximately 80 participants per pilot and to gather quantitative and qualitative results. Furthermore, the METICOS ecosystem aims to work closely with other border control research initiatives to demonstrate its operational performance improvements by means of combined validation with these solutions.

Real travellers will be able to participate in the METICOS activities if they wish to (more details on this are provided under section 3.4 of this deliverable).

Project's description indicates that any research findings generated during the project's life shall focus on the social and technology acceptance of modern no gate technologies at borders.

6.2 Likelihood of incidental findings in METICOS

Given the project's description, it is unlikely that any anticipable incidental findings will occur throughout its duration. More specifically, as mentioned in the previous sections of this report, as the METICOS research findings focus on social and technology acceptance of modern no gate technologies at borders by means of workshops, interviews, questionnaires, surveys and social media crawling, the sole incidental findings that may occur are information derived from the participation of the volunteers or from their public social media information.

Further, it is not anticipated or planned to process any medical data during the METICOS project.

In any case, any unexpected information ie health data, Schengen ban etc that may arise during the process of measuring social and technology acceptance of modern no gate technologies at borders will not be processed further by METICOS researchers to avoid discovering incidental findings.

It is also highlighted that METICOS will abide to the minimisation principle and will collect only data that are relevant for the purposes of the project. In addition, all personal data collected will be anonymised following the initial collection of such data by the responsible partner. Therefore, one will not be able to identify the data subjects which will limit the likelihood of finding any further unexpected information that may lead to incidental findings in relation to such data subjects.

6.3 Procedure to comply with the obligation regarding incidental findings

Incidental findings are traditionally defined as “results that arise that are outside the original purpose for which the test or procedure was conducted”. In the previous sections, it was demonstrated that the scenario of discovering incidental findings during METICOS research has low probability to occur. However, following the EC’s guidelines regarding ethical compliance, it is recommended that a self-risk assessment is performed in METICOS concerning this matter. The following questionnaire could be used to facilitating in minimizing the chances of incidental findings occurrence, even though not anticipated:

Question	Yes/NO
Does METICOS research involve human participants?	Yes
Will clinical or other test be performed on human subjects during the research?	No
Do you expect the discovery of any incidental findings? If yes please provide details of such findings.	No
In the event of discovery of incidental findings do you have the resources and experts to classify and evaluate them?	Yes
In the event of discovery of incidental findings do you have a management plan available?	Yes
In the event of discovery of incidental findings do you have a communication/disclosure policy available?	Yes
Have you provided for the right person (physician or other individuals with scientific training) qualified to communicate such findings to the subjects concerned, if this is required?	Yes
Have you included information regarding incidental findings in the consent forms you acquire from the data subjects?	Yes

As mentioned above, in the METICOS project, in an unlikely event of any incidental finding raising ethical concerns discovered throughout the execution of the project, the following policy will apply:

- 1) In a first place, this incidental finding will be immediately referred to:

- the project's coordinator: Pantelis Velanas (may be contracted at P.Velanas@research.euc.ac.cy); and
- the project ethics responsible partner: Vrije Universiteit Brussel (may be contacted at franck.dumortier@vub.be); and
- the European Commission, in its funding agency capacity, via the project officer

with the view to evaluate their ethical implications and to reach a decision on further action.

2) Secondly, the following rules will govern any incidental findings:

- Individuals in controlled tests will give an informed consent to take part in the research;
- Deletion of any incidental findings will be considered by the bodies mentioned in (1);
- In case of incidental findings that include recording an illegal activity, the consortium will comply with all relevant local and international laws;
- In case of incidental findings that include any information of public interest, the bodies mentioned in (1) would make a decision about the need, means and timing of their communication to relevant stakeholders.

This policy might be revised and adjusted throughout the lifetime of the METICOS project, should this prove necessary.

7 Conclusions

The most important information presented in this deliverable is that:

METICOS Project understand the requirement of obtaining informed consent to involve research participants.

As a consequence, it has been concluded that the METICOS project, in fulfilment of this ethic requirement, is reporting in this deliverable an analysis of H - Requirement No. 2 in relation of the planned research activities involving human participants.

This deliverable has also applied the definition of incidental findings to the research context, and has brought forward the basic elements of a relevant policy. However, after juxtaposition between these elements and the METICOS project description it has been established that there is only a low probability that any incidental findings shall occur during the project execution. Notwithstanding this conclusion, in case incidental findings arise, a procedure has been defined and communicated to all project partners.

APPENDIX: Samples of the METICOS’ information sheet and informed consent forms

METICOS Information Sheet template

METICOS Information Sheet

Project Title:

METICOS: A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

You are invited to participate in a research study being conducted as part of the research project METICOS. The project is coordinated by the European University of Cyprus (EUC) and is funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 scheme (Grand Agreement number 883075). The project began on 01/09/2020 and will come to an end on 31/08/2023. You can find more about the project at website <https://meticos-project.eu/>.

Purpose of the document

The purpose of this document is to provide you a relevant information about objectives of METICOS project, the nature of your participation to METICOS activities, the personal data that will be collected and used by the METICOS platform and how the data will be protected to ensure data confidentiality and privacy as well as what are your rights with respect to your participation.

The METICOS: Concepts and objectives

The purpose of the METICOS platform is to conduct scientific research exploring both travellers’ and border control staff ‘s attitudes about border control technologies in order to measure technology acceptance and efficiency. The proposed platform will provide aggregated metrics and KPIs to authorities and decision makers, based on a number of independent variables: performance expectancy, effort expectancy, facilitating conditions, physical privacy, accuracy, information privacy, as well as ethical and societal perceptions.

The METICOS joint controllers

The joint controllers of the METICOS platform are EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY CYPRUS (EUC), INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS (ICCS), NET-U CONSULTANTS LTD (NetU), NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU (NTNU), SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL (SIMAVI), AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH (AIT), JOHANNITER OSTERREICH AUSBILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH (JOAFG) and MAGGIOLI SPA (MAGG).

The METICOS joint controllers agreed that EUC may be contacted by the data subjects and represent the other joint controllers. The person to be contacted is the coordinator of the project, Pantelis Velanas. (may be contacted at P.Velanas@research.euc.ac.cy).

Basis of lawfulness

The basis of lawfulness for the collection of primary data is your consent. The basis of lawfulness for the collection of secondary data (twitter data) is the legitimate interest of the METICOS joint controllers to further process public data for scientific and statistical purposes.

Incidental findings

During the processing of your data, incidental findings may be found. In the event such incidental findings arise, this will be reported to the responsible persons and the European Commission. Findings will be evaluated and their deletion and communication to you will be considered. In case of incidental findings that include recording an illegal activity, METICOS will comply with all relevant local and international laws.

Recipients

Only authorized researchers of METICOS joint controllers' organizations will have access to the primary and secondary data being collected. Border control authorities and other decision makers will be provided only with anonymized metrics and KPIs.

Transborder data flows

No data transfers outside the European Union are being envisaged.

Data retention period

At the latest, personal data concerning you will be deleted four months after the end of the project.

Purposes of your participation

The purpose of your participation is to contribute to the validation of the technology acceptance, the social acceptance and to enhance the trust to Smart Border solutions by civilians from different cultures. The information collected during the study will be gathered together and used to contribute towards the project, its reports and a number of journal and conference publications. None of the information will identify you individually but will be analysed at an aggregate level.

[The information sheet shall be amended to provide for the required wording for each activity for the participant to understand the nature of participation in the research and the types of personal data that are collected:

WORKSHOPS AND INTERVIEWS;

You will be asked to participate in METICOS pilot that will take place at [place] on [time]. During the pilots you will be asked to use the available equipment in your capacity as a [border control officer OR traveller].

You will be asked to complete a questionnaire on the technologies and their applicability and usability in relation to the Border Control Points.

The data collected by METICOS:

The data to be collected will not contain any personal or sensitive information that can identify you. Any personal information (eg. Name, contact details etc) that may be collected from you is for our internal processing and administrative purposes only, and to enable to contact you if we require further information.

AND/OR**QUESTIONNAIRES AND SURVEYS;****Nature of participation:**

You will be asked to complete a questionnaire that will post questions in relation to border control points technologies, their efficiencies and societal acceptance.

The data collected by METICOS:

The data to be collected will not contain any personal or sensitive information that can identify you. Any personal information (eg. Name, contact details etc) that may be collected from you is for our internal processing and administrative purposes only, and to enable to contact you if we require further information.

AND/OR**PILOTS****Nature of participation:**

You will be asked to participate in METICOS pilot that will take place at [place] on [time]. During the pilots you will be asked to use the available equipment in your capacity as a [border control officer OR traveller].

You will be asked to provide your feedback and input on the efficiency and acceptance of such equipment by completing a questionnaire.

If you agree to take part to this activity, any personal information (eg. Name, contact details etc) that may be collected from you is for our internal processing and administrative purposes only, and to enable to contact you if we require further information.

The data collected during the METICOS pilots:

Two categories of data are being processed by the METICOS platform: primary and secondary data. Primary data are collected directly from participants whereas secondary data consist into statistical data as well as public data being further processed for the purpose of the METICOS platform.

More precisely:

- Primary data consist into the personal data collected via questionnaires, the METICOS Mobile Application and the METICOS Tablet application. The categories of data concerned are: time to cross the border, demographics & profile, smiley face, structured data in form of Likert Scale/ Ticking boxes (including questions regarding speed (queue, waiting time ?), accuracy, efficiency, user friendliness, data protection, privacy, ethical perception of traveler for the specific technology (and potentially generally). Moreover, some examples of questions may include: What are the main problems when crossing the border in general and have the SBC managed to resolve some? Which type of biometrics are you more in favour of? What kind of difficulties you encounter when using SBC? How important do you think speed/privacy/data protection/security/trustworthiness is in the context of SBC implementation? Was there sufficient and efficient communication signs? Any impact on personal health/wellbeing? Was there the adequate guidance needed?) and unstructured data in form of free text questions (Some examples of questions asked may include: In your opinion, the advantages of SBC outweigh the disadvantages and why? What problems have you encountered while using SBC technologies? Give a short review of your experience with SBC today. What did you like/not like?). In

addition, the METICOS platform may process tweets posted by the participant after crossing the border in the BCP METICOS pilot site, a using the #METICOS-EU_pilot hashtag.

- Secondary data consist into:
 - Public tweets (or other public social media) collected for a long period of time which concern the public and societal acceptance of border control technologies. The METICOS platform downloads any related tweets periodically. The data retrieved are the date and time the tweet has been posted, the tweet's text, the tweet ID, number of retweets and likes, and the tweet's location. All other information is discarded. The aim is to process the tweet's text and derive the overall sentiment of the tweets, their geographic distribution and the context of discussion (most popular hashtags and mentions, topics people are tweeting about, entities identified in text, such as people, locations, organizations etc.). After having retrieved the above information, the tweets are deleted. The only information being kept is the aggregated results from the analysis performed above (sentiment, context of discussion, geographic distribution).
 - Online reviews which concern specific BCPs (airports/ports/land borders) published on websites and blogs.
 - Statistical and anonymized data originating from the border crossing points' databases.]

Your rights

During the trials, any participant who wishes to not to continue the trials will have the right to do so, without having to give explanations and without being affected in any way.

A participant may not be able to exercise their rights of access, rectification or erasure of his/her data as no data that could be used to identify that person will be collected. To exercise such rights, the participant may be required to provide additional information to enable his/her identification from the data collected by the METICOS joint controllers.

Contacts for further information and complaint

If you have any further question, you can contact any member of the METICOS research team. Moreover, to file a formal complaint, please contact any of the METICOS team representatives below:

1. Project coordinator

- Pantelis Velanas (may be contacted at P.Velanas@research.euc.ac.cy)

2. Project data protection responsible partner:

- Vrije Universiteit Brussel (may be contacted at franck.dumortier@vub.be)

3. Contact details of [Data Protection Officer of the activity's responsible partner]:

- [name, organisation name (may by contacted at [email])]

You also have the right to lodge a complaint with your data protection authority.

Thank you for taking part in the METICOS research.

Yours sincerely,

METICOS team

Informed consent form for participation in research**METICOS informed consent template**

Project Title:

METICOS: A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

I, undersigned

[name]

[date of birth]

hereby give my consent to take part in the research carried out by the METICOS Research Consortium under the following conditions (**please tick box as appropriate**):

1. I have been informed that the METICOS (A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Control Technology) is a Research & Innovation Action No. {883075} to be run under the European Union Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (Topic SU-BES01-2019). The coordinator of the Research and Innovation Action is European University of Cyprus (Diogenis Str 6 Nicosia CY, 2404, Cyprus), represented by Dr. Pantelis Velanas).
2. I confirm that I am an adult (over 18 years old).
3. I have been informed about the purposes of the project, the activities to which I am involved and the purposes of my involvement to those activities.
4. I have been informed of the details of the research activity I will be participating.
5. I have had all my questions answered to my satisfaction.
6. I have been informed that I can also address any ethical questions or concerns arising from this research by means of contacting the coordinator.
7. My participation in the research will include the processing of personal data as described in the Information Sheet.
8. I understand that my data will be made available only to the members of the METICOS Research Consortium and to the European Commission.
9. I understand that any further use of this information will require my separate consent.

10. In the event of incidental findings I understand that such findings will be communicated to the Project Coordinator and Ethics Manager of METICOS and to the European Commission and will be handled in accordance with applicable legislation. I consent that I do not wish to receive information on the occurrence of such incidental findings.
11. I understand [I will / I will not] be paid for my participation.
12. I participate in this research activity voluntarily.
13. I give this consent fully informed, freely and voluntarily.
14. I understand that it is not feasible for me to exercise my rights to access, rectification or erasure of my data in the event that it is not possible to identify me from the data collected by the METICOS joint controllers unless I can provide additional information enabling my identification.
15. I hereby, agree to give personalized permission to METICOS to collect and process my personal data as provided in the Information Sheet and in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation.

Participant: _____

Name of Participant

Signature

Date

METICOS team representative:

Name of representative

Signature

Date